

Recent Developments in Quantum Chaos of Mixed-Type Systems: A Mini Review

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We review recent developments in quantum chaos of generic systems, i.e. mixed-type systems whose classical counterparts have a divided phase space, where regular and chaotic regions coexist. We consider the energy level statistics, the Wigner and Husimi functions of the eigenstates, the localization properties of chaotic eigenstates in the phase space, their statistical properties and the power-law decay of the proportion of the mixed eigenstates in the semiclassical limit. These results confirm the prediction of the *Principle of uniform semiclassical condensation* (PUSC), which predicts the existence of either regular or chaotic Wigner and Husimi functions in the semiclassical limit, with vanishing fraction of the mixed states. These observations have been recently found in billiard systems, in quantum kicked top and in the Dicke model.

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1. Introduction

It is a nice opportunity to write a review paper on the occasion of publishing the 100th issue of our Journal Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems. On this occasion it is a pleasure to congratulate the entire Editorial Team for the great efforts and excellent work in so successfully running the journal.

In 1998, after the foundation of the Journal under the leadership of late Professor Vyacheslav Kuvshinov, I had the honor to write the first paper (page 1) for the first issue (No 1) and the first volume (Vol 1) of JNPCS, where I have explicitly formulated the *Principle of Uniform Semiclassical Condensation* (PUSC) of Wigner or Husimi functions in the semiclassical limit in the generic case of mixed-type systems [1]. Since then, in the past 25 years a lot of work has been performed on various aspects of quantum chaos, especially regarding the semiclassical limiting behaviour. Most recently [2–4], it has been shown that, indeed, the fraction of mixed-type eigenstates decays in the semiclassical limit as a

power law, as a function of an effective Planck constant. Moreover, the Husimi functions of the chaotic eigenstates are typically localized, and in the limiting case (regime) of uniform chaoticity (if no sticky regions exist) their localization measures display the universal beta distribution, as demonstrated in billiards [5, 6], in kicked top [7] and Dicke model [8]. The rough criterion for the quantum or dynamical localization of the chaotic eigenstates in the phase space is that the Heisenberg time (see below) must be shorter than the classical transport time, or diffusion time, in the classical phase space of the corresponding classical system. If this criterion is not satisfied, we observe uniformly spread Wigner or Husimi functions over the classically available chaotic region in the phase space, which always happens in the sufficiently deep semiclassical limit, for a sufficiently small effective Planck constant. The beta distribution then collapses to the Dirac delta distribution peaked at the maximum localization measure.

Quantum chaos, or more generally wave chaos, is an established field of research in

physics [9–12]. The existence of dynamical chaos in quantum mechanics is still a subject of current debates. The sensitive dependence of time evolution (solution of time dependent Schrödinger equation) as an analogy of classical chaos certainly does not exist, because the overlap of two initial states remains rigorously constant due to the unitary time evolution. Also, of course, the analogy of classical orbits does not exist in quantum mechanics due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Nevertheless, recently there is an increased interest in the so-called out-of-time ordered correlator (OTOC), introduced by Larkin and Ovchinnikov [13, 14], which sometimes behaves exponentially if the corresponding classical system has positive Lyapunov exponents, but not always, and always certainly only up to some finite time scale, usually the Ehrenfest time. This subject is considered as an indicator of quantum chaos, especially in many body systems, although it has been found that there is no one-to-one correspondence between the classical positive Lyapunov exponents and the exponential behavior of OTOC. Namely, there are systems with classical zero Lyapunov exponents but exponential OTOC of the quantum correspondent, for example the recently studied polygonal billiards in Ref. [15], where the references to earlier relevant works can be found. Also, the authors of Ref. [16] report on nonexponential behavior of OTOC in the stadium billiard of Bunimovich [17] which is classically chaotic with positive Lyapunov exponents.

The stationary quantum chaos is well established analogy of the classical chaos in Hamiltonian systems [9–12, 18]. Namely, we find phenomena in the solutions of the time independent Schrödinger equation which correspond exactly to the classical structures. Such signatures of classical chaos are found in the statistical properties of the energy spectra, in the structure of corresponding eigenfunctions and of their Wigner functions [19] or Husimi functions [20]. For example, the classically integrable systems exhibit Poisson statistics of the unfolded (reduced to unit mean level spacing) energy

spectra, their wave functions have a well ordered structure of nodal lines or surfaces, and their Wigner or Husimi functions are localized near the invariant tori in the classical phase space. On the other hand, in the opposite case of classically fully chaotic (ergodic) systems the energy spectra obey the statistics of random matrices, especially - but not only - of the Gaussian random matrices, the nodal patterns of eigenfunctions are entirely disordered and their probability amplitude exhibits a Gaussian random function [21]. Their Wigner or Husimi functions are ergodic, in the sense that they are on the average uniformly spread over the energy surface in the classical phase space. For a review see Ref. [1, 11, 18].

The above statements are valid under an important *semiclassical condition*, namely that the dominating classical diffusion time or transport time t_T is sufficiently shorter than the Heisenberg time t_H , which by definition is $t_H = 2\pi\hbar/\Delta E$, where ΔE is the mean level spacing, or inverse energy level density $\rho(E) = 1/\Delta E$. In such case, if the semiclassical condition is satisfied, all the above statements for fully chaotic systems have been proven to be rigorously true using the semiclassical methods, in particular Gutzwiller's semiclassical theory of expressing the quantum Green function, and its trace $\rho(E)$, in terms of classical periodic orbits [22–26]. For fully chaotic systems, satisfying the semiclassical condition, this proof was initiated by Berry [27] in 1985, further developed by Sieber and Richter [28] in 2001, and completed by the group of Haake [29–32] in the years 2004–2010 [10]. Therefore the well known Bohigas-Giannoni-Schmit conjecture [33], initiated by Casati, Valz-Gris and Guarneri [34], can be considered as proven.

Let us recall that the Heisenberg time goes to infinity when \hbar goes to zero, because $\Delta E \propto \hbar^f$ and f is the number of degrees of freedom, $f \geq 2$, as we do not consider the systems having one degree of freedom. Thus, in the semiclassical limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$, the Heisenberg time $t_H \propto \hbar^{1-f}$ eventually becomes larger than any classical transport time of the system t_T , as the latter one does not depend

on \hbar . Their ratio

$$\alpha = \frac{t_H}{t_T} = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{\Delta E t_T}, \quad (1.1)$$

is the important parameter characterizing the deepness of the semiclassical regime. Thus the semiclassical condition is $\alpha \gg 1$. In such case the Principle of Uniform Semiclassical Condensation (PUSC) [1] of Wigner functions applies, saying that the Wigner functions become uniformly spread over the classical invariant component in the phase space, based on works by Percival [35], Berry [21, 36], Shnirelman [37], Voros [38], and further developed by Veble, Robnik and Liu [39]. This can be an invariant torus, a chaotic component, or the entire energy surface, depending on the dynamical properties and the structure of phase space (integrable, mixed-type or ergodic). If the semiclassical condition $\alpha \geq 1$ is not satisfied, we observe localization properties of the chaotic eigenstates uncovered in the Wigner functions or Husimi functions in the phase space: The Wigner or Husimi functions are concentrated on a proper subset of the available classically chaotic region. In fact, the transition from strong localization at $\alpha \ll 1$ to strong delocalization at $\alpha \gg 1$ is a rather smooth one, as observed recently in several model systems. A study of these effects in an ergodic billiard system with strong stickiness has been performed in a series of our recent papers [5, 6, 40–43]. The stickiness implies nonuniversal behavior of the statistics of the energy spectra and of the localization measure. The degree of localization can be quantified in at least three different ways: entropy localization measure A , correlation localization measure C , and the normalized inverse participation ratio $R = nIPR$. We have shown [6, 41, 42] that they are linearly related and thus equivalent. In case of uniform chaoticity (no stickiness) in ergodic systems but with slow chaos, A obeys the beta distribution [6], which collapses to a Dirac delta distribution in the limit of effective Planck constant \hbar going to zero. The regime of localized eigenstates exhibits

also different behavior of the energy spectra: the level spacing distribution $P(S)$ is no longer linear at small S , but behaves as a fractional power law $P(S) \propto S^\beta$ with $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$. In case of strongest localization $\beta = 0$ and we observe Poissonian statistics, while in case of full chaos and maximal extendedness $\beta = 1$ and we see the statistics of random matrices. For larger values of S the distribution can be very well (semi-empirically) approximated by the Brody distribution [5, 6, 44, 45] to be defined below.

However, the classically integrable and classically chaotic ergodic systems are rather exceptional, although very important, as the typical (generic) Hamilton systems realized in nature are of the mixed-type, having divided phase space: the classically chaotic regions in the phase space coexist with the classically regular regions. KAM-scenario [46] gives a typical picture showing the extremely complex structure of the invariant components in the classical phase space, with an infinite statistically self-similar hierarchy of islands of stability and chaotic components. Such systems have been studied for the first time in the context of quantum chaos by Berry and Robnik in 1984 [47]. Meanwhile the literature on this problem has become quite extensive – for a recent review see Ref. [11, 18, 48].

The paper is organized as follows. In Sec. 2 we consider the statistical properties of energy spectra. In Sec. 3 we consider the Wigner and Husimi functions, their structure and their localization properties, in particular the connection between the degree of localization of chaotic eigenstates and the level repulsion exponent appearing the corresponding level spacing distribution. In Sec. 4 we introduce the overlap index M which measures the overlap of Wigner or Husimi functions with the classical regular and chaotic components. We study its statistical properties and their behaviour in the semiclassical limit. In particular, we show in several model systems (lemon billiards, kicked top and Dicke model) that the relative fraction of the mixed-type eigenstates decays as a power-law in the semiclassical limit, as a function of an effective

Planck constant. These results are in agreement with the predictions of PUSC. In Sec. 5 we present further comments regarding the interpretation of the results and present the discussion, conclusions and outlook.

2. Statistical properties of the energy spectra

It is a well known result from the early days of quantum chaos in the 1980s, that the discrete energy spectra of bound quantum systems obey the statistical properties of the Gaussian random matrices if the corresponding classical system is ergodic and chaotic [33, 34], the so-called BGS (Bohigas–Giannoni–Schmit) conjecture. Here we must assume that the energy spectra have been unfolded, that is the mean energy level spacing reduced to unity. Only then universality of spectral fluctuations can be uncovered. Of course, also the energy level density of Gaussian random matrices is not physical, and what we mean in this context is the spectral fluctuation properties of the eigenvalues of random matrices.

This came as a surprise, as the random matrices [49] have been invented by Wigner to describe the statistical properties of complex many-body systems like complex atomic nuclei, while the chaotic dynamical systems can be even just one-particle system with just two degrees of freedom, like e.g. simple chaotic two-dimensional billiard systems. As explained above, for this to be true the α parameter must be sufficiently large, larger than 1. If the underlying quantum system has time reversal symmetry or any other antiunitary symmetry the appropriate ensemble of Gaussian random matrices is the GOE (Gaussian Orthogonal Ensemble), while if the system lacks an antiunitary symmetry the appropriate ensemble is the GUE (Gaussian Unitary Ensemble). (We ignore spin, and consider only spin-less systems.) In the case of GOE, the infinite dimensional level spacing distribution is very well approximated by its two-dimensional version [12], given by the celebrated Wigner

distribution

$$P_W(S) = \frac{\pi S}{2} \exp\left(-\frac{\pi S^2}{4}\right), \quad (2.1)$$

where the linear level repulsion phenomenon is clearly demonstrated by the behavior at small S . Important quantity is also the corresponding gap probability, i.e. the probability that an interval of length S is empty of levels,

$$\mathcal{E}_W(S) = 1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}S}{2}\right) = \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}S}{2}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

There is a entirely general relationship between these two quantities, namely $P(S) = d^2\mathcal{E}(S)/dS^2$ (see e.g. [9, 10]).

On the other hand, classically integrable systems have spectra which are regarded as entirely uncorrelated “events”, which can be understood in terms of semiclassical torus quantization (EBK, Einstein-Brillouin-Keller), implying the Poissonian level spacing distribution and the related gap probability,

$$\mathcal{E}(S) = \exp(-S), \quad P(S) = \exp(-S). \quad (2.3)$$

If the system is of the mixed type where regular and chaotic regions coexist in the classical phase space, then in the semiclassical limit we can assume statistically independent superposition of the Poissonian sequence and the GOE sequences [47], with relative density of levels equal to the relative phase space volume (Liouville volume) of each component (subsequence). For two components, just one regular with relative density μ_1 and one chaotic with relative density $\mu_2 = 1 - \mu_1$, the gap probability factorizes due to the statistical independence, and we obtain

$$\mathcal{E}(S) = \mathcal{E}_P(\mu_1 S) \mathcal{E}_W(\mu_2 S) = \exp(-\mu_1 S) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}\mu_2 S}{2}\right). \quad (2.4)$$

and consequently [47], using $P(S) = d^2\mathcal{E}(S)/dS^2$,

$$P_{BR}(S) = e^{-\mu_1 S} e^{-\frac{\pi\mu_2^2 S^2}{4}} \left(2\mu_1\mu_2 + \frac{\pi\mu_2^3 S}{2} \right) + e^{-\mu_1 S} \mu_1^2 \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}\mu_2 S}{2} \right). \quad (2.5)$$

This theory is well tested, especially in references [50, 51].

Things become more complicated in cases of dynamically localized chaotic eigenstates, which emerge when $\alpha < 1$. It turns out, phenomenologically, that in such case the level spacing distribution of the chaotic subsequence is well described by the Brody distribution

$$P_B(S) = C_1 S^\beta \exp(-C_2 S^{\beta+1}), \quad (2.6)$$

where the two parameters C_1 and C_2 are determined by the two normalizations $\langle 1 \rangle = \langle S \rangle = 1$, namely we have $C_2 = \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{\beta+2}{\beta+1}\right) \right]^{\beta+1}$, and $C_1 = (\beta+1)C_2$. The corresponding gap probability is

$$E_B(S) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{\beta+1}\right)} Q\left(\frac{1}{\beta+1}, (\alpha S)^{\beta+1}\right) \quad (2.7)$$

where $Q(a, x)$ is the incomplete Gamma function

$$Q(a, x) = \int_x^\infty t^{a-1} e^{-t} dt. \quad (2.8)$$

Here β is the level repulsion exponent in (2.6), which also measures the degree of localization of the chaotic eigenstates: if the localization is the strongest, the eigenstates practically do not overlap in the phase space (of the Wigner functions) and we find $\beta = 0$ and Poissonian distribution, while in the case of maximal uniform extendedness (no localization) we have $\beta = 1$, and the GOE statistics of levels applies. Thus, by replacing $E_W(S)$ with $E_B(S)$ we get the BRB (Berry-Robnik-Brody) distribution, which generalizes the Berry-Robnik distribution such that the localization effects are included [40]. This BRB distribution has been numerically proven to well describe the spectra with divided phase space and the dynamical localization of the chaotic part [40].

3. Wigner and Husimi functions, PUSC, and phase space localization of chaotic eigenstates

To study the relationship between the quantum systems and the corresponding classical systems in the semiclassical limit, it is necessary to introduce some kind of quantum phase space. This is achieved by introducing the Wigner functions [19], and the Husimi functions [20], the latter ones being just the Gaussian smoothed Wigner functions.

3.1. Wigner functions

We define the **Wigner functions of eigenstates**, in terms of the orthonormal eigenfunctions $\psi_n(\mathbf{q})$ in configuration space, in the *quantum phase space* (\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) , as follows:

$$W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^N} \int d^N \mathbf{X} \exp\left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{X}\right) \times \psi_n\left(\mathbf{q} - \frac{\mathbf{X}}{2}\right) \psi_n^*\left(\mathbf{q} + \frac{\mathbf{X}}{2}\right) \quad (3.1)$$

They are real valued but **not positive definite**, and possess the following properties:

- (P1) $\int W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) d^N \mathbf{p} = |\psi_n(\mathbf{q})|^2$ (= probability density in configuration space)
- (P2) $\int W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) d^N \mathbf{q} = |\phi_n(\mathbf{p})|^2$ (= probability density in momentum space)
- (P3) $\int W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} = 1$ (normalization)
- (P4) $(2\pi\hbar)^N \int d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) W_m(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \delta_{nm}$ (orthogonality)
- (P5) $|W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})| \leq \frac{1}{(\pi\hbar)^N}$ (no singularities; Cauchy-Schwartz inequality)
- (P6 = P4) $\int W_n^2(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^N}$ (divergence in the limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$)
- (P7) $\hbar \rightarrow 0$: $W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) \rightarrow (2\pi\hbar)^N W_n^2(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) > 0$ (positivity in the limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$)

From this we see that in the semiclassical limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ the Wigner function becomes predominantly positive definite, that it is supported in a volume cell of size $(2\pi\hbar)^N$,

and thus *condenses* in such a cell. Since the Wigner functions are orthogonal, they must "live" in disjoint supports and therefore become statistically independent of each other. The question is, what is the geometry/structure of such a cell.

3.2. PUSC of Wigner functions

The Principle of Uniform Semiclassical Condensation (PUSC) of Wigner functions of eigenstates is based on the papers by Percival [35], Berry [21, 36], Shnirelman [37], Voros [38], Robnik [1], and Veble, Robnik and Liu [39]. It states that the Wigner function $W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})$ condenses uniformly on a classical invariant component in the classical phase space, when $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ and if $t_H > t_T$. The invariant component can be an N -dimensional invariant torus, a chaotic component, or the entire energy surface in the case of classical ergodicity:

(C1) Invariant N -torus (integrable or KAM):

$$W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^N} \delta(\mathbf{I}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) - \mathbf{I}_n). \quad (3.2)$$

(C2) Uniform on a chaotic region:

$$W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{\delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})) \chi_\omega(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})}{\int d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} \delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})) \chi_\omega(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})}$$

where $\chi_\omega(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})$ is the characteristic function on the chaotic component labeled by ω

(C3) Ergodicity (microcanonical Wigner function):

$$W_n(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{\delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}))}{\int d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} \delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}))} \quad (3.3)$$

Here we also define μ as the relative Liouville measure of the relevant classical invariant component indexed by ω :

$$\mu(\omega) = \frac{\int d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} \delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})) \chi_\omega(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p})}{\int d^N \mathbf{q} d^N \mathbf{p} \delta(E_n - H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}))} \quad (3.4)$$

This principle has a great predictive power, as shown e.g. in [39]. The important condition for

the uniformity of the Wigner functions of chaotic eigenstates is: The Heisenberg time t_H must be larger than classical transport time scales t_T , thus $\alpha > 1$. It is also the theoretical basis for deriving the Berry-Robnik distribution (2.5) and the BRB distribution.

3.3. Poincaré-Husimi functions

To calculate the Wigner functions or the Husimi functions is a task specific for each individual system. In the case of two-dimensional billiards the formalism is particularly elegant and effective, therefore here we shall restrict the discussion to two-dimensional billiards.

Let us consider 2D billiard, using the natural coordinates in the phase space (s, p) : the arclength s round the billiard boundary, $s \in [0, \mathcal{L}]$, where \mathcal{L} is the circumference, and the sine of the reflection angle, which also is the component of the unit velocity vector tangent to the boundary at the collision point, equal to p . These coordinates are canonically conjugate, known as the Poincaré-Birkhoff coordinates. The bounce map $(s_1, p_1) \rightarrow (s_2, p_2)$ is area preserving [52], and the phase portrait does not depend on the energy. For the quantum billiard we have to solve the stationary Schrödinger equation, which (using the appropriate units) reduces to the Helmholtz equation $\Delta\psi + k^2\psi = 0$ with the Dirichlet boundary conditions $\psi|_{\partial\mathcal{B}} = 0$. The energy is $E = k^2$. The important quantity is the boundary function

$$u(s) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \psi(\mathbf{r}(s)), \quad (3.5)$$

which is the normal derivative of the wavefunction ψ at the point s (\mathbf{n} is the outward unit normal vector). The boundary function $u(s)$ satisfies the integral equation

$$u(s) = -2 \oint dt u(t) \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}(t)), \quad (3.6)$$

where $G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = -\frac{i}{4} H_0^{(1)}(k|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|)$ is the Green function in terms of the Hankel function $H_0(x)$. The boundary function $u(s)$ contains complete

information about the quantum system, because the wavefunction at any point \mathbf{q} inside the billiard can be determined by the equation [53]

$$\psi_j(\mathbf{r}) = - \oint dt u_j(t) G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}(t)). \quad (3.7)$$

When going over to the quantum phase space we can calculate the Wigner functions based on $\psi_n(\mathbf{r})$ and perform the procedure developed in the previous section. However, in billiards it is advantageous to calculate the Poincaré–Husimi functions, which are generally just Gaussian smoothed Wigner functions. Such smoothing makes them positive definite, so that we can treat them as quasi-probability densities in the quantum phase space. Following Tualle and Voros [54] and Bäcker *et al.* [55], we use [41] the properly \mathcal{L} -periodized coherent states centered at (q, p) , as follows

$$c_{(q,p),k}(s) = \sum_{m \in \mathbf{Z}} \exp\{i k p (s - q + m\mathcal{L})\} \times \exp\left(-\frac{k}{2}(s - q + m\mathcal{L})^2\right). \quad (3.8)$$

The Poincaré–Husimi function is defined as the absolute square of the projection of the boundary function $u(s)$ onto the coherent state, namely

$$H_j(q, p) = \left| \int_{\partial\mathcal{B}} c_{(q,p),k_j}(s) u_j(s) ds \right|^2. \quad (3.9)$$

In figure 1 we show examples of a regular and of a chaotic eigenstate for the billiard introduced by Robnik in [56, 57], which is the conformal complex map $w = z + \lambda z^2$ of the unit disc $|z| = 1$. Here we take the shape parameter $\lambda = 0.15$.

Now we can classify the eigenstates as regular and chaotic according to their overlap with the regular regions or chaotic regions. According to PUCS, in the ultimate semiclassical limit we expect only purely regular and purely chaotic eigenstates. However, before reaching this limit we observe also mixed states, which overlap with both, regular and chaotic regions. Their characterization will be performed quantitatively in the next Section, by introducing the overlap

index M . But we should emphasize already at this point that the relative fraction of the mixed states decays with an effective Planck constant as a power law, where the exponent is system dependent [2–4].

3.4. Phase space localization of chaotic Poincaré–Husimi functions

The chaotic eigenstates exemplified by the chaotic state in Fig. 1 can be localized, which is a stationary aspect of the quantum or dynamical localization, as explained in the Introduction. To quantify the degree of localization we introduce three different localization measure, which are almost equivalent.

We express the localization measures in terms of the discretized and normalized Husimi function. For the *entropy localization measure* denoted by A we write $A = e^{\langle I \rangle} / N_c$, where $I = - \int dq dp H(q, p) \ln((2\pi\hbar)^f H(q, p))$ is the information entropy and N_c is a number of cells on the classical chaotic domain. The mean $\langle I \rangle$ is obtained by averaging I over a sufficiently large number of consecutive chaotic eigenstates. In the case of uniform distribution $H_{ij} = 1/N_C$ the localization measure is $A = 1$, while in the case of the strongest localization $I = 0$, and $A = 1/N_C \approx 0$.

The *correlation localization measure*, denoted by C , is defined by the overlap (correlation matrix) $C_{nm} = \frac{1}{Q_n Q_m} \sum_{ij} H_{ij}^n H_{ij}^m$, where $Q_n = \sqrt{\sum_{ij} (H_{ij}^n)^2}$ is the normalizing factor. Then $C = \langle C_{nm} \rangle$, and the averaging is over all n, m and a large number of consecutive chaotic eigenstates.

The *normalized inverse participatio ratio* also is almost linearly related to A and C , as mentioned in the introduction, but we shall no longer pursue it here.

Again we use the same billiard with $\lambda = 0.15$. For a good approximation of the localization measures A and C it was sufficient to separate and extract about 1.500 consecutive chaotic eigenstates. The two localization measures are

FIG. 1. Poincaré-Husimi functions of a chaotic (left) and regular (right) eigenstate, for the Robnik billiard at $\lambda = 0.15$. The values $k(M)$ are: chaotic: $k(M) = 2000.0181794$ (0.981); regular: $k(M) = 2000.0777155$ (-0.821). The gray background is the classically chaotic invariant component. Only one quarter of the surface of section is shown, $(s, p) \in [0, \mathcal{L}/2] \times [0, 1]$, since due to the reflection symmetry and time-reversal symmetry the four quadrants are equivalent. Taken from [41].

linearly equivalent as shown in figure 2. In order to calculate β with sufficient accuracy we need much more levels, and therefore the separation of eigenstates is then technically too demanding. We have instead calculated spectra on small intervals around $k \approx 2000$ and $k \approx 4000$, about 100.000 consecutive levels (no separation), and obtained β by fitting the $P(S)$ by the BRB distribution derived in section 2 using the classical μ_1 . The functional dependence of β on A is shown in figure 2. For aesthetic reasons we have rescaled the measure $A \rightarrow A/A_{\max}$ such that it goes from 0 to 1. The maximal value of A , $A_{\max} = 0.68$, was estimated as $A_{\max} = e^{I_{\max}}/N_c$, where I_{\max} is the maximum entropy of 1500 consecutive states of the almost fully chaotic $\lambda = 0.25$ billiard. Thus for fully chaotic systems the procedure always yields $A = 1$. Namely, in real chaotic eigenstates we never reach a perfectly uniform (constant) distribution $H(q, p)$, since their Poincaré-Husimi functions always have some oscillatory structure.

Let us look at the functional relationship between A and β , as shown in figure 2. By increasing k from 2000 to 4000 we increase the dimensionless Heisenberg time by factor 2, therefore A must increase, but precisely in such a way, that the empirical points stay on the scaling curve, as it is observed and indicated by the arrows. We do not have yet a semiempirical functional description of the relationship $\beta(A)$. In the quantum kicked rotator it is just almost linear [58–60]. Similarly it is found to be almost linear in the stadium of Bunimovich, as recently published

in reference [43] and shown in figure 3. The level repulsion exponent β is also found to be a unique function of $\alpha = t_H/t_T$, well described empirically by the rational function

$$\beta = \beta_{\infty} \frac{s\alpha}{1 + s\alpha}, \quad (3.10)$$

as shown in figure 4, discussed in reference [43]. There is a great lack in theoretical understanding of the physical origin of the relationship $\beta(A)$, even in the case of (the long standing research on) the quantum kicked rotator, except for the intuitive idea, that energy spectral properties should be only a function of the degree of localization, because the localization gradually decouples the energy eigenstates and levels, switching the linear level repulsion $\beta = 1$ (extendedness) to a power law level repulsion with exponent $\beta < 1$ (localization). The full physical explanation is open for the future.

One should notice some scattering of points around the mean value in the figure 4, noted already by Izrailev [58] in the case of the quantum kicked rotator, which indicates that the localization measure has a certain distribution rather than being a sharp number, as has been observed recently in the kicked rotator by Manos and Robnik [61]. In the next section we address the question of the statistical properties of the localization measure A .

FIG. 2. Quantum localization in the Robnik billiard $\lambda = 0.15$, using about 1500 consecutive chaotic eigenstates. (Left:) Linear relation between the two entirely different localization measures, namely the entropy measure A and the correlation measure C , calculated for several different billiards at $k \approx 2000$ and $k \approx 4000$. (Right:) We show the functional relation between the Brody level repulsion parameter β and A . Arrows connect points corresponding to the same λ at two different k . Taken from [42].

FIG. 3. The Brody parameter β as a function of the localization measure A for a large number of stadium billiards of different shapes ε and energies $E = k^2$. Taken from [6].

3.5. Statistical properties of the localization measures

Recently we have shown two important results. The first one is the empirical observation

FIG. 4. The Brody parameter β is a rational function of α (3.10), where t_T is extracted from the exponential diffusion law, for a large number of stadium billiards of different shapes ε and energies $E = k^2$, as in figure 3. Here $\beta_\infty = 0.98$ and $s = 0.20$. Taken from [43].

[5], in the billiard family devised and studied in [56, 57], that the localization measures A of chaotic eigenstates have a distribution, which generally speaking depends strongly on the

structure of the classical phase space, namely on the existence of the stickiness regions in the chaotic component. However, if the chaotic region becomes uniformly chaotic, ergodic without stickiness, we find universality: The distribution function of A , $P(A)$, is the *beta distribution* on a compact interval $[0, A_0]$, where A_0 is empirically found to be around $A_0 \approx 0.7$. The beta distribution is defined as

$$P(A) = CA^a(A_0 - A)^b, \quad (3.11)$$

and the two exponents a and b are positive real numbers, while C is the normalization constant such that $\int_0^{A_0} P(A) dA = 1$, i.e.

$$C^{-1} = A_0^{a+b+1} B(a+1, b+1), \quad (3.12)$$

where $B(x, y) = \int_0^1 t^{x-1}(1-t)^{y-1} dt$ is the beta function. In figure 5 we show the results for the distribution $P(A)$ of the chaotic eigenstates for three different mixed-type lemon billiards (for the definition see e.g. Appendix A in Ref. [2]) at three different energies $E_0 = k_0^2$, and the excellent agreement with the best fitting beta distribution is obvious. For the details see [62]. In the ultimate semiclassical limit the beta distribution approaches the Dirac delta distribution $\delta(A_0 - A)$ peaked at the maximum value of $A = A_0 \approx 0.7$.

The second result is that the entire picture does not depend much, very weakly, on the definition of the localization measure A , so that e.g. the same conclusions can be met by using the normalized inverse participation ratio, rather than the (Shannon, information) entropy localization measure. It has been demonstrated [5, 6, 8] that the entropy localization measure and the normalized inverse participation ratio are almost linearly related.

These results have been reconfirmed in the stadium billiard of Bunimovich [6], and in the family of lemon billiards [63], as well as in the Dicke model [8] and in kicked top [7]. Therefore, we believe that this is a universal behaviour.

4. The overlap index M and its statistics

4.1. The definition of the overlap index M and separation of eigenstates

Now we can quantitatively classify the eigenstates as regular and chaotic according to their projection onto the classical surface of section. As we are very deep in the semiclassical regime we can expect with probability almost one that either an eigenstate is regular or chaotic, with exceptions having measure zero, ideally. To automate this technical task we have ascribed to each point on the grid of the classical phase portrait a number $A_{i,j}$ whose value is either $+1$ if the grid point lies within the classical chaotic region or -1 if it belongs to a classical regular region. This has been done as follows. We have taken an initial condition in the chaotic region, and iterated it up to about 10^{10} collisions, enough for the convergence such that we are not missing any chaotic cells. Each visited cell (i, j) on the grid has then been assigned value $A_{i,j} = +1$, the remaining ones were assigned the value -1 .

The Poincaré Husimi function $H(q, p)$ (3.9) (normalized) has been calculated on the grid points and the overlap index M has been calculated according to the definition $M = \sum_{i,j} H_{i,j} A_{i,j}$. In practice, M is not exactly $+1$ or -1 , but can have a value in between. There are two reasons: the finite discretization of the phase space (the finite size grid), and the finite wavelength (not sufficiently small effective Planck constant, for which we can take just $1/k$). If so, the question is, where to cut the distribution of the M -values, at the threshold value M_t , such that all states with $M < M_t$ are declared regular and those with $M > M_t$ chaotic.

We have considered two natural criteria: **(I)** *The classical criterion:* the threshold value M_t is chosen such that we have exactly μ_1 fraction of regular levels and $\mu_2 = 1 - \mu_1$ of chaotic levels. **(II)** *The quantum criterion:* we choose M_t such that we get the best possible agreement of the chaotic level spacing distribution with the Brody

FIG. 5. The histograms $P(A)$ of the chaotic eigenstates for the mixed-type lemon billiards $B = 0.42$ (first row), $B = 0.55$ (second row), and $B = 0.6$ (third row), at various energies $E_0 = k_0^2$: (a,d,g) $k_0 = 640$, (b,e,h) $k_0 = 1760$, and (c,f,i) $k_0 = 2880$. All states are of odd-odd parity. The agreement with the best fitting beta distribution is obvious. The parameters (a, b) of the beta distribution (3.11) are, from (a) to (i): (20.100, 12.380), (44.209, 29.091), (59.477, 40.172), (28.982, 22.380), (52.361, 39.027), (80.315, 57.947), (31.734, 19.835), (63.872, 41.757), (90.748, 59.885). Taken from [62].

distribution (2.6).

Using this method we can separate the regular and chaotic eigenstates and the corresponding eigenvalues, using the classical criterion (I). The corresponding threshold value of the index M is found to be $M_t = 0.431$. The level spacing distributions are shown in figure 6. We see perfect agreement with Brody distribution with $\beta = 0.444$ for the chaotic levels and almost perfect Poisson distribution for the regular levels. The agreement with Poisson and Brody is due to the fact that the relative number of mixed states is very small. See the next Subsection. These findings corroborate the theory of energy level statistics in Sec. 2.

FIG. 6. Level spacing distributions for separated chaotic (left) and regular (right) levels in the Robnik billiard with $\lambda = 0.15$. We use the classical separation criterion with $M_t = 0.431$. For the chaotic subspectrum, after unfolding, there is perfect agreement with the Brody distribution with $\beta = 0.444$. For the regular part of the spectrum, after unfolding, we see excellent agreement with Poisson. Taken from [42].

FIG. 7. (central) color-plot of the histogram of the joint probability density $P(A, M)$ for approximately 10^6 eigenstates with unfolded energy $e \in [10^4, 10^6]$ of the $B = 0.1953$ lemon billiard. The color scale of the main figure is logarithmic. PH functions of the highest energy eigenstates within small boxes at various positions are shown on the margin. Their corresponding wavenumbers are (a) $k = 4598.5120$, (b) $k = 4638.3417$, (c) $k = 3486.3962$, (d) $k = 4637.4426$, (e) $k = 4610.3436$, (f) $k = 4603.9386$, (g) $k = 4050.5505$, (h) $k = 4636.9990$, (i) $k = 4637.1017$, (j) $k = 4236.8109$, (k) $k = 4638.4472$, (l) $k = 3776.8166$. A classical phase portrait is plotted in the background of each state for comparison. The color scale at the bottom encodes the relative amplitude of the PH function. Taken from [2].

4.2. The statistics of the overlap index M and its semiclassical behavior

In a recent work [2] we have performed a detailed phenomenological analysis, in lemon billiards, of various regular, chaotic and mixed eigenstates, by looking at their Poincaré-Husimi functions, and also their corresponding A and M values in a joint two-parameter space. The result is shown in Figs. 7 and 8, where the distribution of eigenstates clearly shows two clouds of states, those at small A and M , corresponding to regular states, and those at largest values of A and M , corresponding to chaotic states. In between there are mixed states for which A and M obtain

intermediate values. However, their proportion decreases with the decreasing value of the effective Planck constant, or with increasing unfolded energy e .

This is in perfect agreement with PUCS, their relative fraction decays, in the semiclassical limit, as a power law with exponent approximately $\gamma \approx -0.3$ as a function of the unfolded energy (which also is the number of consecutive energy levels). This is shown in Fig. 9 for the two lemon billiards $B = 0.1953$ and $B = 0.083$. In (a) the mixed states are taken in the interval $M \in [-0.8, 0.8]$ for the lemon billiard $B = 0.1953$ and $M \in [-0.8, 0.1]$ for the lemon billiard $B = .0083$, which was chosen based on

FIG. 8. (central) color-plot of the histogram of the joint probability density $P(A, M)$ for approximately 10^6 eigenstates with unfolded energy $e \in [10^4, 10^6]$ of the $B = 0.083$ lemon billiard. The color scale of the main figure is logarithmic. PH functions of the highest energy eigenstates within small boxes at various positions are shown on the margin. Their corresponding wavenumbers are (a) $k = 4221.4610$, (b) $k = 4253.9880$, (c) $k = 4227.7699$, (d) $k = 2649.8961$, (e) $k = 4250.2980$, (f) $k = 4254.5877$, (g) $k = 4113.9895$, (h) $k = 4254.0666$, (i) $k = 2126.9352$, (j) $k = 4255.2063$, (k) $k = 4255.6550$, (l) $k = 4181.7921$. A classical phase portrait is plotted in the background of each state for comparison. The color scale at the bottom encodes the relative amplitude of the PH function. Taken from [2].

the visual inspection of Figs. 7 and 8. In (b) we show how the exponent γ depends on other choices of the relevant M -interval, for smaller intervals. For details see [2].

Let us mention that such a power-law decay of the mixed states in the semiclassical limit has been found also in other systems, like kicked rotator and the Dicke model [3, 4], as well as in the Henon–Heiles system [64].

5. Discussion, conclusions and outlook

The earliest works on quantum chaos of mixed-type (generic) systems are the references [47, 56, 57]. Knowing the results for the classically integrable and chaotic systems, Poissonian and the GOE statistics [33, 34], respectively, the spectral statistics of mixed-type systems in the sufficiently deep semiclassical limit, with no localization and no tunneling effects, has been established and later also confirmed in billiard model systems [50, 50, 51]. The semiclassical behavior of eigenstates in the quantum phase space has been summarized in the *Principle of*

FIG. 9. Decay of the relative number of mixed states with energy. (a) The relative number of states in the interval as a function of unfolded energy. Both decay exponents are close to $\gamma = -0.29$. (b) Decay exponents for smaller intervals $[M, M + \delta M]$ with $\delta M = 0.1$. Taken from [2].

Uniform Semiclassical Condensation ((PUSC) of Wigner or Husimi functions, formulated in reference [1], which has been widely confirmed in a series of phenomenological, numerical, studies of various systems, billiard systems, quantum kicked top, Dicke model etc. The theoretical phenomenological description of mixed-type systems has then been generalized to include the tunneling effects at low energies [40], as well as the phase-space localization effects of chaotic eigenstates (their Wigner or Husimi functions) [41, 42]. It has been very well established that the level spacings distribution $P(S)$ of chaotic eigenstates is well captured by the Brody distribution, which at small spacings goes as a power $\propto S^\beta$, where the level repulsion exponent β is in the interval $[0, 1]$: in the case of strongest localization $\beta = 0$, implying Poisson statistics,

while for fully chaotic states $\beta = 1$, implying the Wigner distribution which is very close to GOE. Furthermore, it has been found that β is a (almost linear) function of the mean localization measure A . Moreover, A has a distribution, which is system dependent and specific [65], but becomes a beta distribution in case of uniform chaoticity (no stickiness effects in the classical phase space). In the ultimate semiclassical limit it becomes a Dirac delta distribution peaked at the maximal value of A . To quantify the distribution of eigenstates as for their relationship to the classical phase portrait we have introduced the overlap index M , which ideally (in the ultimate semiclassical limit) is either -1 (for regular states on invariant tori) or $+1$ for chaotic states, but before reaching that limiting behavior it can also obtain intermediate values $-1 < M < +1$ for the mixed states. The distribution $P(M)$ is strongly doubly peaked near -1 and $+1$, and the fraction of the intermediate values of M corresponding to the mixed eigenstates decays as a power law as a function of the effective Planck constant, or increasing unfolded energy, with an exponent which is system dependent, and can be related to the structure of cantori in the stickiness regions of the classical phase portrait - see [2–4, 64] and the references therein. These findings are in perfect agreement with PUSC.

There are many open challenging theoretical questions: derive the localization properties of chaotic eigenstates, both, the Brody distribution for the level spacing distribution, and the beta distribution of the localization measure, and the power-law decay of the mixed-type eigenstates. Our recent and current efforts are directed towards this goal, while many numerical studies in various model systems are on the way, corroborating the above conclusions.

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